

ChromoScope: A Graphic Interactive Browser for E. coli Data Expressed in the NCBI Data Model

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An interactive graphic viewer, ChromoScope, was developed to explore scientific visualization of complicated genome data. Escherichia coli was selected as the test organism. An ASN.1 data set has been built for the entire E. coli chromosome, including a genetic map, a physical (ordered restriction) map, the alignment between the two maps, Kohara clones and some short repeat features. The E. coli sequence is modeled as a segmented sequence, incorporating both the sequence and the physical map data. The alignment between the contig and the published sequences is stored as sequence history, allowing direct access to the same sequence in the public databases. The alignment is displayed graphically, with both the sequence alignment and feature annotations. The alignment viewer also supports a detailed text display, providing information to resolution at residue level with annotated features.

1: Introduction

With the advance of molecular biology, it is likely that complete genomic sequence data for some model organisms will soon be available. Genome data is characterized by heterogeneity, rapid change and quantity. It is accumulated from different research groups and from different domains of biology, ranging over genetic map, physical map, DNA sequence, coding region and protein products. It has applications in agriculture and medical science. Available data is growing rapidly as research progresses and new technologies are developed. Genome data can be very large. An organism as small as Escherichia coli has about 4,670,000 base pairs, which is about 1% of the size of human genome. The complexity of genome data makes a difficult challenge for data management and software development.

To meet this challenge, National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) has developed a sequence data model which provides a unified concept for

a variety of sequence data. The data model is specified in ASN.1 (Abstract Syntax Notation). Under this model, sequence data is treated as a simple, linear coordinate system. Genetic map, physical map and composite assemblies of sequences are all considered simply subclasses of the basic sequence class. Relationships between the sequences can be considered to be mappings from one coordinate system to the other with associated attributes. The data hierarchy from the chromosomal level, to contigs on a chromosome, to individual sequence entries can be presented in the same way. Information about the sequence can be considered as mappings of specialized data objects such as publication, gene, coding regions to particular regions in the sequence, thus, a very wide range of data can be associated with a simple core and connections can be made between different disciplines in genome research. The data model makes an integrated high level view of genome data, any related information can be referenced through the coordinate system.

To explore the properties of the NCBI sequence data model in handling complicated genome data, we chose Escherichia coli as the test organism to build an ASN.1 data model for the whole genome. For this organism, a high resolution restriction map (Kohara *et al.* 1987) and a very comprehensive genetic map (Bachmann, 1990) are available. More than 50% of the whole genome (~4,670,000 base pairs) has been sequenced. Its genome is large enough to represent most of the complexities in biological data. Its genome has been well organized already. Rudd *et al.* (1990) have aligned the restriction map with the genetic map and compiled a non-redundant sequence library named EcoSeq which includes all the contigs on the non-redundant E. coli sequence map. A relational data model has been built and all those data are stored in Sybase. From the EcoSeq database, we built ASN.1 data models for the integrated E. coli genome data. Those data are used as input for ChromoScope, a sophisticated interactive graphic viewer which provides access to integrated E. coli data at three different levels: chromosome, contig and individual sequence.

Figure 1. System overview of ChromoScope

Figure 2. Relationship between the ASN.1 data and the Graphic Interface in ChromoScope.

ChromoScope allows the user to browse over 1511 genes, 476 Kohara clones, 7882 restriction sites, 897 multiple sequence alignments involving 2367 sequences, 5995 DNA and protein sequence records, 4399 MEDLINE records, 733 short repeat sequences known as chi elements (sequences involved in recombination) and REP elements (Repetitive Extragenic Palindromic). A graphic tool for sequence alignment was developed which can display both aligned sequences and their associated features, so the user can analyze the effect of sequence differences (unpublished). ChromoScope was written in using the NCBI software toolkit, which means it can run on Mac, PC, UNIX Motif and VMS.

2: System overview

Figure 1 depicts the interaction of user-interface, application program and I/O in ChromoScope system. Two ASN.1 structures E. coli.ent, EcoMap.ent were loaded into memory to provide the E. coli genome data at the chromosomal level. E. coli.ent contains instructions for building a non-redundant E. coli sequence map, while EcoMap.ent provides the data of genetic map, physical map and their alignment with each other. Published sequence data can be retrieved as needed from either Entrez:Sequences CD-ROM or Entrez NetWork Service. Each of the contigs on the non-redundant E. coli sequence map is stored as an ASN.1 text file containing sequence, its features and its alignment to other published sequences.

The graphic interface is implemented in Vibrant, a high level, multi-platform user interface library developed by Jonathan Kans at NCBI. Vibrant acts as an intermediate between the application program and the underlying windowing systems. Everything in the published user interface guideline for the various window systems is taken care of automatically, so the host window system is invisible to ChromoScope.

ChromoScope is currently running on UNIX under X11 OpenWindow, on Macintosh and under Microsoft Windows on PC.

3: Data model design

The general scheme of ChromoScope is shown in Figure 2. All the input data are expressed in the ASN.1 data model. The complicated relationship between the different genome data is preserved in the hierarchy of the ASN.1 structure. The data model Seq-entry is able to handle a biological sequence in different representation classes, from chromosomes to restriction fragments, from genetic maps to proteins, DNA sequences. In our system, all the ASN.1 text files for Seq-entry are named with an

extension .ent. The E. coli chromosome can be presented as a restriction map, a genetic map or a DNA sequence. EcoMap.ent stores the information for both the restriction map and the genetic map, which are two approaches to present the same entity: the E. coli chromosome. All the information are referenced in the base-pair coordinate system. The linkage between the two maps is preserved by aligning all the genes on one map to the other. Another set of data, Kohara clones, was used to construct the restriction map. The alignment between a clone and the restriction map shows the history of how a fragment on the restriction map was derived by digesting a clone with eight restriction enzymes. The short repeat sequences, such as REP elements or chi elements, are treated as features of the chromosome. They are attached to the restriction map by their locations and orientations. In EcoMap.ent, gene, restriction site, Kohara clone, repeat sequence are linked by referencing the same coordinate system. However, since the genetic map is originally recorded in the 0-100 minute coordinates, EcoMap.ent stores a Numbering object for presentation to the user of genetic map locations in genetic minute.

Both the genetic map and the restriction map are relatively stable, however, the sequence data are still incomplete and evolves with progress in the E. coli sequencing. E. coli.ent models this unstable entity in the form of a segmented sequence. It uses the same base-pair coordinate system as the EcoMap.ent. For an unsequenced segment, E. coli.ent points to the corresponding region on the restriction map; for a sequenced segment, it references a contig by the sequence identifier. Under this model, the E. coli sequence map can be easily updated by replacing a map segment with a sequence segment which references the new contig.

Each contig on the non-redundant E. coli sequence is represented as a separate Seq-entry. The collection of all contigs is named EcoSeq.ent. Some of the contigs (571 out of 897) are published sequences but re-annotated in the EcoSeq database. The Seq-entry for each contigs stores the re-annotated feature tables and the alignment between the entry and other published sequences. Its sequence data is presented by referencing the sequence identifier to its published counterpart. For the other entries, sequence data is stored as well as the feature annotation and sequence alignment. If an entry is created by melding several smaller pieces of DNA sequences, it is modeled as a constructed sequence.

The sequence identifiers for published entries enables ChromoScope to take advantage of the NCBI data access functions. A published record can be retrieved by its sequence identifier from Entrez CDROM or from Entrez Network Service. The direct link between ChromoScope and the Entrez:Sequence ensures that the user gets the up-

Figure 3. The global view of *E. coli* genome

Figure 4. The genetic map, the sequence map and their alignment

to-date information of the *E. coli* records, currently including 5995 DNA and protein records and 4965 MEDLINE records, rather than requiring a large database of this dynamic dataset be maintained locally.

3: Functionality and Implementation

The graphic interface of ChromoScope is implemented in three layers (Figure 2), the user is able to access *E. coli* genome data from the complete chromosome to single residue in a sequence. As the program starts, *Draw_Circle* shows the global view of the circular *E. coli* chromosome (Figure 3). The user can select a region on the circle with the mouse, and *Draw_Big_Seq* will display an integrated map of the user-defined region (Figure 4, 5, 6, 7). By selecting a contig on the map, *Show_Alignment* will display the alignment of a contig with the published *E. coli* entries (Figure 8). *Show_Alignment* also supports ASCII output of the alignment (Figure 9). Each sequence in the alignment can be displayed either in GenBank format or in Report format using standard NCBI toolkit functions (Figure 10). The design and functionality of each module is discussed in detail below.

3.1: Draw_Circle

Draw_Circle displays a global view of the complete *E. coli* chromosome as shown in Figure 3. The green circle labeled with 500 kb tick marks, represents the 4,670,000 base-pair *E. coli* K12 genome. Outside the green circle, there is a layer of black arcs. Each arc represents a sequenced region while a gap between two adjacent arcs indicates an unsequenced region. Ten landmark genes taken from the default text file *gene.lst* are displayed on the big circle; as an option, the user can select an additional gene of interest to be labeled together with the landmark genes. The user can also make his or her own gene list instead of using the default file.

Draw_Circle uses the ASN.1 data structure from the file *Ecoli.ent* to get the information about the sequenced and unsequenced segments. By traversing through the *Ecoli.ent*, the location of each contig on the chromosome can be calculated as [start, stop] in base pair coordinates, which can be mapped into the corresponding position on the circle. A similar mapping mechanism is used to place genes on the circle. All the genes on the chromosome are stored as a feature table in *Ecoli.ent*. By exploring the feature table of *Ecoli.ent*, the requested genes can be filtered out. In a feature table, the location is stored in an ASN.1 object *Seq-loc*. As a convention, the start of the gene feature is taken as the gene's position on the circle.

Draw_Circle is implemented on an autonomous panel of the Vibrant Panel objects. A rubber-band function is

implemented with Click, Drag, Release callback, so the user can select a rectangular region on the panel. If the user-selected region has no intersection with the circle, an error message will complain about the user's choice. Once the user selected region is determined, *Draw_Big_Seq* will display an integrated *E. coli* map of that region. For example, if a researcher is interested in sequencing a gap on the map, he can select the gaps on the circle for additional information. If another researcher is interested in knowing all the available data for a certain gene, she can label the gene on the circle, and select the region surrounding the gene for more details.

3.2: Draw_Big_Seq

Draw_Big_Seq gives a comprehensive view of the *E. coli* chromosome, which includes the genetic map, the sequence map, the alignment between the two maps; the history of each contig on the sequence; the annotated features such as protein, ORF, RNA and DNA sites on the region; the eight-enzyme restriction map; the short repeat features; the Kohara clones. All these data are included in the various ASN.1 objects in *EcoMap.ent*, *Ecoli.ent*, *EcoSeq.ent* as described in Data Model Design.

The graphic interface is implemented using the Vibrant viewer objects. It supports the definition of graphic objects in world coordinates (in our system, base-pair coordinates can be mapped directly into the world coordinates), autonomous zooming and scrolling, and interaction with the graphic using a mouse. Figure 4, 5, 6, 7 are the screen copies of the *Draw_Big_Seq* output, discussed in detail in the following five sections.

3.2a The restriction map, the genetic map and their alignment: The genetic map and its alignment to the sequence map is shown in Figure 4 and Figure 7. On the genetic map, the locus name of a gene is labeled and its position is marked in minute coordinates. If a gene's position in the sequence map is also known, a black line connects the two positions showing the alignment between the two maps. If the start of the gene on the sequence map is not within the user-defined region, a green line to either end will indicate the "out of scope alignment". For example, in Figure 7, gene *pcnB* is aligned out of the left border. Figure 5 shows the standard Kohara restriction map with eight enzymes. Each enzyme is marked in a different color for a better visual effect.

The input data for the restriction map, genetic map and their alignments comes from *EcoMap.ent*. By traversing the genetic map and restriction map stored in *EcoMap.ent*, the data for the two maps and their alignment within the user-defined region can be readily located. Each gene position on the genetic map is marked in the 0-100 minute

Figure 5. The Restriction map, repeat sequence features and Kohara clones.

Figure 6. The pop-up message for feature description.

Figure 7. The output of a refined region

Figure 8. The graphic display of sequence alignment with user-selected features

coordinate system, the conversion is provided by the Numbering object stored in genetic map. On some occasions, in the genetic map, there are multiple genes at one location because conjugation experiments can only map genes with low resolution. To prevent those genes from overwriting each other, the number of preceding genes in the same location is determined and the current gene is placed on top of the stack. Several stacking genes is shown in Figure 4, one example is the deoCABD cluster. From the alignment, it is clear that those genes are in different locations on the sequence map.

3.2b The sequence map, its history and features: Below the genetic map, is the non-redundant E. coli sequence map (Figure 4, 7). The scaler for the sequence map changes in response to the user-selected zooming value. A red line with an arrow represents a contig, which is a sequenced region on the chromosome. The arrow indicates the orientation of the contig on the chromosome. The locus name or the accession number of each contig is also labeled. Below the red line is the history of a contig, which is the alignment between a contig and the published sequences in GenBank. If an aligned component is used in EcoSeq to construct the contig, a green line will mark the aligned region, otherwise a black line will be used. The user can click on the contig or any of its aligned sequences to get the graphic display of the sequence alignment.

Following the "sequence history" are the features of the sequence map (Figure 5, 6). Different colors are used to distinguish different feature types. If the user requires more detailed information, he can click on the feature, and a pop-up message will give a brief feature description. As illustrated in Figure 6, the user will be informed with the type of feature, its location and orientation on the contig, the name of the protein and the synonyms of the gene name.

The sequence map is implemented in a fashion similar to that is described for *Draw_Circle*. However, if the end of a contig is out of the user-defined boundary, only the location within the boundary will be processed. When a contig is processed, its Seq-entry is loaded into memory by reading the EcoSeq.ent ASN.1 file. The ASN.1 objects for sequence history and features can be retrieved from the Seq-entry. After the boundary is adjusted, each object can be mapped from its location on the contig to its position on the sequence map. The Seq-entry will be freed before the next process starts. For an unsequenced region, there is no sequence history and the features come from the feature table for the restriction map stored in EcoMap.ent. The ASN.1 data model of segmented sequences allows *Draw_Big_Seq* to process one segment at a time, each Seq-entry will be retrieved when necessary

and freed when the process is over, which saves precious memory for processing such a huge volume of data.

The locations of graphic objects presenting a contig, its history and features are attached to the viewer. Whenever the user clicks on the screen, the viewer is able to identify the graphic object and determine which type of data the object presents.

3.2c Kohara clones and the repeat sequence features: Both the Kohara clones and the repeat sequences are shown in Figure 6, below the restriction map. A black line with an arrow presents each clone, the arrow is the orientation of a clone on the chromosome. REP and chi elements are indicated in different colored lines. Some of these REP clusters are only about 20-40 bp long, if a large zoom-out value is selected, they only appear as small dots. For a clone, the user can click and get a message for the clone name and length.

Kohara clones are stored as the history of the restriction map in EcoMap.ent, repeat sequences are in the feature table of the restriction map. Their positions on the chromosome can be mapped to the viewer's world coordinates. The location of the graphic object representing Kohara clones is stored, which can be identified when the mouse clicks.

3.2d Mouse interactive callback functions for Draw_Big_Seq: *Draw_Big_Seq* allows the user to rubber-band a region or to click on a object. If the user rubber-bands to select a sub-region, a window pops up showing the orientation of the features and the alignments in addition to all the other information (Figure 7). The radio buttons on top allow the user to select one of the five feature types. When the user clicks on the sequence history to show the graphic display, this feature type will be shown together with the sequence alignment (Figure 8).

To distinguish a rubber-band operation click, drag, release from a simple click operation, the point where the mouse clicks and the point where it releases are compared. If the distance between the two is less than 10 pixels, the user is doing a simple click. The viewer identifies the graphic object where the mouse was clicked. If the object has a parent, it is an alignment object, otherwise it is either a feature or a clone. For an alignment object, *Show_Alignment* will be called to show the graphic display of the alignment. For a feature or a clone, the point can be mapped to its position on the chromosome. The annotation can be located quickly by traversing the feature table for a feature or the history of the restriction map for a clone.

If the user selects a sub-region by rubber-banding, the start and stop can also be mapped to the chromosome. The

picture for the sub-region is created using the same function as *Draw_Big_Seq*, except flags are set on to show the orientations of features and alignments and five radio buttons allow the user to select features to be displayed together with sequence alignment: "Protein" which translates all the coding regions into protein products, "Coding Region" marks all the coding regions, Gene marks all the genes, "RNA" marks all the RNA features, "Other" marks the named regions. In order to avoid indefinite rubber-banding, the drag and release callback is not implemented. The click callback performs the same function as the simple clicks for the *Draw_Big_Seq*.

3.2e Cross the "zero": Although the *E. coli* map is internally a linear coordinate system, ChromoScope allows the user to view and manipulate subregions crossing the zero point in a continuous manner, modeling the circular biological molecule in a natural and intuitive way. (Figure. 4)

3.3: Show_Alignment

The graphic output of the sequence alignment is shown in Figure 8. The black rectangle is the master sequence (ES1161 in Figure 8), which in ChromoScope system, is a contig on the *E. coli* chromosome. All the aligned sequences are shown below the master. A scaler marks the position of the master sequence, which changes with the user-selected zooming value. The name and the orientation of each sequence is labeled. A mismatch in an alignment is marked in a vertical red line within the horizontal bar of the sequence (X05810, X04319 in Figure 8), a gap is a straight line connecting the two fragments (X05810 in Figure 8), an insertion is marked by a vertical line connecting to the inserted fragment to the alignment (M12486, X05810). The picture also displays sequence features along with the alignment. In Figure 8, "Protein" is selected. Each feature is marked in a different color for better visual distinction. If the user clicks on the feature , a pop-up message describes the name, orientation, location of that feature. This allows the user to compare the annotations of the same feature in different sequence records.

If the user wants to view the alignment in detail, a sub region can be rubber-banded and a pop-up window shows the text output of the alignment. The text alignment gives resolution at the residue level, so the user will know exactly the changes (Figure 9). The feature display helps the user to analyze the effect of sequence differences. In Figure 9, the coding regions are translated into proteins. At the position of the arrow, there is a gap in sequence X05810, which causes a frame-shift in the *fhuC* protein

sequence. This frame-shift is corrected by an insertion at position 876 in X05810.

If the user wishes to view each sequence record, he can select the radio button "GenBank" or "Report" for the desired format. Each Seq-entry can be readily convert into GenBank flatfile, even though for an EcoSeq entry, the file does not yet exist in the GenBank database (Figure 10).

The user-interface of *Show_Alignment* is implemented in Vibrant's viewer object. The alignment data is stored as a history of the sequence in *EcoSeq.ent* built for each contig. The alignment is a multiple pairwise alignment. In order to show the relationship between the master sequence and each component, the master is presented intact with no insertions and deletions. This means sequence aligned to the master must be displayed showing both deletions and insertions. Most alignment display can show only deletions. To compute the mismatches in the alignment and display the features, all the sequences need to be retrieved; for an EcoSeq entry, an Seq-entry will be loaded into memory by reading its *EcoSeq.ent* ASN.1 text file. The other published sequences can be retrieved by the NCBI data access library, which returns a pointer to the sequence's ASN.1 data on the Entrez:Sequence Disk.

4: Discussion

E. coli data is unique in its richness for sequence information. To present this genome, all the components of ChromoScope were designed at the sequence level. Both the genetic map and physical map are modeled as specialized sequences, the relationship between them can be viewed through their alignment to the sequence map. This is different from the other genome viewers, such as ACeDB, which started as a viewer for the physical map data, then enhanced to present sequence information. ChromoScope does not implement as much graphic interface for physical map data as ACeDB does, it emphasizes more the graphic interface for browsing sequence, from the chromosome level, to contigs, to individual sequences. Each sequence can be accessed directly and the sequence alignment viewer is used to demonstrate the relationship between it and other sequences, showing the biological effect of the insertions, deletions and mismatches. Currently, ChromoScope is a browser for genome data, but we are working toward implementing editing functions to the system.

Most genome viewers, including ACeDB, can only access a data set maintained locally. ChromoScope takes advantage of the Data Access Library functions provided by the NCBI toolkits, and is able to directly access the remote data from GenBank and MEDLINE in addition to the locally maintained EcoSeq data set. This does not only

Figure 11. The global view of the longest contig on chromosome III of *C. elegans*

reduces the volume of local data, but also ensures the user get the latest release of published data.

Because ChromoScope implements the generic NCBI data model, it is not limited to *E. coli* data. As an experiment, we converted the data release 1-21 of *C. elegans* chromosome X and chromosome III (only the largest contig) from ACeDB (Durbin and Thierry-Mieg, 1993) into NCBI data model. We are able to present most of the information except the rearrangement data and the 2-point, 3-point genetic mapping data (Figure 11).

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References

- Bachmann, B. (1990) Linkage map of *Escherichia coli* K12, edition 8. *Microbiol Rev.*, **54**, 130-197.
- Durbin, R. and J. Thierry-Mieg. Unpublished.
- Kans, J. A. (1993) The Vibrant portable user interface. Manuscript in preparation.
- Kohara, Y., Akiyama, K. and Isono, K. (1987) The physical map of the whole *E. coli* chromosome: application of a new strategy for rapid analysis and sorting of a large genomic library. *Cell*, **50**, 495-508.
- Rudd, K. E., Miller, W., Ostell, J. and Benson, D. S. (1990) Alignment of *Escherichia coli* K12 DNA sequences to a genomic restriction map. *Nucleic Acids Res.*, **18**, 313-321.